

Nature-based solutions performance versus man-made hazards:

a literature review for enhancing the resilience of critical infrastructure.

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ABSTRACT: Policymakers in Europe and beyond prioritize nature-based solutions (NBS) as a crucial strategy to tackle societal challenges, including mitigating the impact of climate change and contributing to the achievement of international goals. Risk management and resilience can be improved over conventional approaches, which is of utmost importance today, as Europe is not only confronted with several natural hazards but also with man-made threats. Therefore, to ensure the maximum effectivity of NBS, it is crucial to comprehend and enhance their capacity for preventing and enduring malicious attacks. Specifically, this paper lays the foundation for the Horizon Europe project titled "City nature-based solutions integration to local urban infrastructure protection for a climate-resilient society" (NBSINFRA). The paper explores the role of NBS in safeguarding infrastructure against man-made hazards while simultaneously being susceptible to such threats. Results revealed NBS interventions that effectively mitigate such threats and other NBS more vulnerable to man-made hazards, jeopardizing public safety and contributing to criminal activities if inadequately designed. Based on this review of the literature, landscape architecture and NBS implementation seem to already exploring how the integration of nature and urban environments can safeguard cities and their inhabitants not only from natural hazards but also potential human-made risks.

KEYWORDS: Nature-based Solutions; NBS; Man-made Hazards; Literature Review; Infrastructure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Critical infrastructure consists of assets or systems that are vital to the maintenance of certain societal functions. Natural disasters, criminal activity, or malicious behaviour may damage infrastructure, resulting in its destruction or disruption, which may severely impact the safety and well-being of citizens [1]. The protection of critical infrastructure as well as the mitigation of disaster impact are both dependent on constant innovation. The international community recognizes the imperative to diminish the risk posed by both natural and man-made hazards, a core principle underscored in the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction [2].

In fact, policymakers in Europe and beyond prioritize nature-based solutions (NBS) as a crucial strategy to tackle various societal challenges, including addressing natural hazards, mitigating the impact of climate change, advancing sustainability goals, and contributing to the achievement of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [3,4]. NBS are a cost-effective way to build infrastructure that is resilient to climate change-induced hazards while benefiting humans and biodiversity [5,6]. By combining NBS with local knowledge, critical infrastructure can be protected from natural and man-made disasters.

With solutions such as these, risk management and resilience can be improved over conventional approaches [7], which is of utmost importance today, as Europe is not only confronted with a number of natural hazards, including pandemics, droughts, heat waves, storms, floods, and wildfires but also with man-made hazards [8].

Nevertheless, disaster risk management and adaptation concentrate on minimizing exposure and vulnerability while enhancing resilience to the potential adverse effects of both natural and man-made hazards. Although it is acknowledged that risks cannot be entirely eradicated, these efforts enable assets to better withstand and cope with such challenges [9].

2. NBSINFRA HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT

The protection of infrastructures against hazards and, in particular, man-made ones, such as terrorism, cyber-attacks, or malicious behaviour, has been a priority of the European Commission with the European Programme for Critical Infrastructure Protection (EPCIP) [10]. Although much effort is being expended in re-naturalizing the infrastructure with NBS (e.g., Langemeyer and Baró [11]), man-made threats, along with natural disasters, pose a potential danger to the operating and monitoring systems of the infrastructure.

Therefore, to ensure the maximum effectiveness of NBS, its capability for preventing malicious attacks and sustaining them must be understood and further developed.

Specifically, this paper lays the foundation for the new Horizon Europe project titled "City nature-based solutions integration to local urban infrastructure protection for a climate-resilient society" (NBSINFRA) that just began in September 2023 (4-year project).

There is indeed a focus on improving resilience in vulnerable infrastructure, and the project's main objective is to enhance the local urban infrastructure protection against natural and man-made hazards through NBS co-design and co-creation for a sustainable and resilient society developing a methodology and toolkit that could serve as a best practice guide.

Existing and new approaches will be tested in five different locations, respectively, Aveiro (PT), Fingal (IE), Prague (CZ), Cologne (DE) and Ruse (BG), in the so-called City Labs.

In particular, a comparison of infrastructure vulnerabilities with and without NBS will be conducted via impact simulations and conditions comparisons. In addition to natural hazards, physical and cyber-physical attacks will be considered threats to the infrastructure and the NBS. For instance, NBS monitoring systems, which would reveal their wider benefits and impacts, may be potential targets of cybercrime and other man-made hazards.

2.1 Scope of the paper

The paper explores the role of NBS in safeguarding specific infrastructure against potential manmade hazards while simultaneously being susceptible to such threats. The purpose of this study is to determine whether NBS for infrastructure is at risk from man-made hazards or if NBS might offer protection from them by examining the available literature on the topic (Fig. 1).

3. METHODOLOGY

A manual review was conducted using three of the most widely used search engines, Web of Science, Google Scholar and Scopus. Keywords utilized in this search included 'Nature-based solution or NBS', 'landscape design', 'man-made or man-made hazards', 'cyber-attack* or cyber threat* or cybersecurity', 'terrorism', 'war*', 'crime' 'infrastructure', 'monitor* OR sensor*', 'risk management'. At the same time, information was collected from online newspapers which reported case studies of real attacks on such infrastructure. Information was collected and clustered into two options. From this operation, the results highlight the successful implementation of NBS in mitigating different manmade hazards and at the same time, the most recurrent human threats they may face.

Two distinct clusters concerning NBS and manmade hazards are delineated: the first cluster pertains to potential attacks on critical infrastructure, which could be mitigated through the deployment of NBS (for instance, the use of wetlands to ram a vehicle); the second cluster addresses the vulnerability of NBS, often monitored through measurements and sensors to counteract natural hazards like floods and heat waves, or disruptions to the functionality of NBS itself (such as cases where hackers may interfere with the operation of valves in an irrigation system supporting a green wall, resulting in the demise of plants).

Figure 1: Benefits of NBS employed in infrastructure protection.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The literature review delineated two primary clusters concerning the correlation between NBS and anthropogenic hazards. The first encompasses publications and instances of successful implementation of design solutions, illustrating how NBS can effectively mitigate manmade threats. The second cluster comprises records detailing the potential susceptibility of NBS to anthropogenic hazards.

3.1 Cluster 1 - NBS for manmade threats mitigation

Through the examination of existing literature, the primary challenges discerned within this cluster revolve around Crime and Terrorism, as evidenced by the findings presented in Table 1. The identified threats, specifically in terms of criminal activities and acts of terrorism, underscore the imperative for a nuanced understanding of how NBS may be influenced by, or conversely, impact these security-related issues. This further emphasizes the need for targeted strategies and adaptive measures to address and mitigate the associated risks effectively.

Table 1: Cluster 1 regarding NBS employed to mitigate and reduce the vulnerability of infrastructure and open spaces to manmade threats.

Manmade threat	Focus	References
Crime	Water security	[12,13]

	Properties and people	[14–17]
	Induced fire	[18]
Terrorism	Vehicle-ramming	[16,19–21]
	Explosive attack	[22,23]

Concerning Cluster 1, specifically within the "Crime" category, a thorough examination has been conducted on three principal issues. Cioffi [13] and Everard et al. [12] underscore the potential endangerment of water infrastructure, emphasizing its impact on water security. Additionally, they advocate for the integration of NBS and efficient water harvesting as viable measures to alleviate and diminish this vulnerability.

An expanding body of literature is investigating the correlation between urban greenspaces and crime, producing contrasted findings [17]. Notably, Venter et al. [15] observed that a greater prevalence of greenery in the vicinity of a building correlates with a decrease in reported crimes, including both violent and property offences; the same outcome resulted from the study of Wolfe and Mennis [14]. A significant correlation was found between the abundance of vegetation and a reduction in assaults, robberies, and burglaries, but not thefts. Urban planning policies could be influenced by this, especially as cities adopt green growth plans, emphasizing the importance of integrating sustainable crime prevention strategies into city planning.

Conversely, Koskela & Pain [24] and Sonti et al. [25] emphasize the potential influence of perceptions or fear of crime stemming from vegetation in neighbourhoods, attributing it to issues such as blind spots and excessive density of vegetation.

Furthermore, Regos [18] has underscored the potential of NBS as a preventive measure to mitigate wildfires increasingly instigated by human activities.

In the context of acts of terrorism within urban environments, particularly in open spaces and pedestrian zones, numerous publications and examples of best practices incorporate NBS.

Notably, Felix et al. [19] or the book of the Center for the Protection of National Infrastructure [20] exemplify how landscape design elements, such as trees and flower boxes, can function as defensive systems to enhance building security. They advocate for the incorporation of elements like elevated planters, trees, and benches or other street furniture as substitutes for bollards to offer perimeter protection for designated structures. These features may possess crash-resistant capabilities, providing the security benefits of crash-rated bollards without overtly signalling their protective function. Anti-terrorism barriers of this nature have been deployed in numerous European cities. Fig. 2 illustrates an example wherein plants are positioned within weathering steel cylinders, striking a balance between accommodating security for critical buildings and their

occupants, and preserving the vibrancy of the public space.

Figure 2: Example of Nature-based solutions installed as anti-terrorism barriers in the city centre of Rimini, Italy. This was an initiative made in 2020 called "Incontro alle barriere" which means "meeting at the barriers". Photo: Felicioni L.

The relevance of landscaping in crime prevention is underscored by the RIBA report [21], providing another illustrative example. As an example, clearing or maintaining vegetation around parking lots may be necessary to ensure clear sightlines, create unobstructed camera views along perimeter fencing, provide patrol space for security guards, and eliminate potential shelter for intruders. Additionally, the addition of water features to the landscape enhances the site not only aesthetically, but also serves as both a habitat for wildlife and a physical barrier against intruders.

Moreover, NBS can serve as effective impediments to establishing blast-resistant infrastructure or buildings, as demonstrated by Koccz et al. [22]. The judicious selection of suitable vegetative species becomes crucial, particularly when employed as a perimeter barrier in the guise of thorny hedges and dense hedgerows. Considerations for the ultimate size and maintenance requirements are necessary to prevent the obstruction of critical sight lines or the creation of potential hiding places. In a broader context, the strategic placement of taller vegetation near buildings is recommended to ensure the preservation of open sight lines [16].

In fact, the use of water and greenery for safeguarding against man-made hazards is not a recent concept in landscape architecture; people have employed this strategy for centuries, evident in structures like citadels or castles. The contemporary challenge lies in embracing an interdisciplinary

approach to adapt this traditional concept to the demands and knowledge of modern urban areas, considering the dynamics of current public spaces. Indeed, Fig. 3 exemplifies an ancient case showcasing the multifaceted application of NBS, extending beyond the mitigation of natural hazards, such as coastal flooding. Notably, the Citadel of Copenhagen in 1807 serves as a historical testament to the dual purpose of NBS, both in defence against military conflicts – exemplified during the Battle of Copenhagen against the United Kingdom – and contemporary employment for flood hazard mitigation. Presently, the terrain depression serves a primary function in addressing flood-related risks.

A contemporary example of NBS deployed for protective purposes is evident in the design of the US embassy in London, United Kingdom. The building is surrounded by a bioswale, primarily implemented for environmental considerations. However, the design is meticulously calibrated to effectively impede any moving vehicle attempting to breach the premises by strategically incorporating features capable of thwarting such attempts across the expanse of meadow grasses.

Figure 3: Close-up detail of the terrain depression and the water moat that surrounds the Citadel of Copenhagen, Denmark. Photo: Rybova B.

3.2 Cluster 2 - NBS threatened by manmade hazards

The primary challenges identified within this second cluster revolve around Crime and Cyber Attacks, as illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2 Cluster 2 regarding NBS potentially threatened by manmade hazards.

Manmade threat	Focus	References
Crime	People	[24,26,27]
Cyber attack	Monitoring systems	[28,29]
	Poisoning	[30]

Concerning the "Crime" category, prominent themes consistently circled around the integration of vegetation characteristics, such as density and height, with factors including illumination, legibility of pedestrian routes, and maintenance practices. These factors, coupled with the absence of signs of incivilities, collectively contribute to a positive perception of space. It is crucial to note that an inadequately designed environment may engender a fear of potential attacks by strangers, as exposed by Koskela & Pain [24] and Hosseinalizadeh [26].

In the "Cyber attack" category, the use of Earth Observation (EO) tools, including satellites and drones, for monitoring distant spots may be susceptible to cyber threats and hacking. Notably, Chrysoulakis et al. [29] underscores that EO presents unexploited possibilities, supplying essential data for evaluating the influence of NBS on urban dynamics, particularly in relation to energy, water, and carbon balances. In the event of a technological breach, there exists the potential for malicious use to disrupt disaster management and relief operations, subsequently amplifying the extent of damage and casualties. Another example is the water infrastructure, which is susceptible to direct targeting or contamination through the introduction of toxic substances or disease-causing agents [30]. Instances of such malicious activities are exemplified by hacker attacks on blue infrastructures, particularly irrigation systems, resulting in the introduction of hazardous amounts of chemicals. A notable episode occurred in Florida in 2021, and this was not an isolated occurrence, with several other incidents documented in Israel [31].

Noteworthy studies, such as those conducted by Koskela & Pain [24] and Ogletree et al. [17], explore public perceptions of greenery in urban environments and its capacity to mitigate criminality and other threats. For a considerable number of respondents, the presence of greenery contributes to a more pleasant and secure environment since the number of crimes reduced after the implementation of new green areas.

Furthermore, proper maintenance of NBS is essential. For instance, inadequate planting of a tree barrier can lead to weakened roots, resulting in reduced shading benefits and a compromised wind-barrier effect. Similarly, the use of low-quality substrate can impede rainwater retention, hindering effective evaporation and diminishing the cooling impact on the city during summer. Additionally, it may compromise trees' ability to provide sufficient protection to pedestrians in the event of a vehicle attack. This principle can be extended analogously to swales and rain gardens.

4. CONCLUSION

This study investigates the dual aspects of NBS in relation to their potential mitigation of, or

susceptibility to, man-made hazards. The literature review reveals two primary clusters: the first emphasizes NBS interventions that effectively mitigate such threats, while the second cluster consists of publications and examples highlighting the vulnerabilities of NBS to man-made hazards, which could pose risks to public safety and contribute to criminal activities if inadequately designed—such as in cases concerning dense vegetation that obscures blind spots.

Based on this review of literature, it is evident that landscape architecture has begun exploring how the integration of nature and urban environments can safeguard cities and their inhabitants not only from natural hazards but also potential human-made risks. Nevertheless, there are relatively few concrete examples of NBS being employed to mitigate manmade hazards.

The insights gathered from this study serve as foundational knowledge for the Horizon Europe NBSINFRA project, designed to enhance infrastructure resilience against both natural and man-made hazards. These findings will be instrumental in guiding the implementation of new NBS within the City Labs' locations but will also steer additional studies and applications of NBS for mitigating man-made hazards in various European contexts.

Future work will delve into the specific probabilities of encountering man-made hazards within the City Labs.

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affairs.ec.europa.eu/pages/page/critical-infrastructure_en [20 June 2023].

2. UNISDR, The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015 - 2030.
3. United Nations, (2015). The Sustainable Development Goals; New York City;
4. Faivre, N.; Fritz, M.; Freitas, T.; de Boissezon, B.; Vandewoestijne, S., (2017). Nature-Based Solutions in the EU: Innovating with nature to address social, economic and environmental challenges. *Environmental Research*, 159, p.509–518, doi:10.1016/j.envres.2017.08.032.

REFERENCES

1. European Commission Critical infrastructure, [Online] Available: [https://home-](https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/pages/page/critical-infrastructure_en)

5. EU-funded OPERANDUM project, [Online], Available <https://www.operandum-project.eu/> (8 July 2023).
6. Dabbeek, J.; Silva, V.; Galasso, C.; Smith, A., (2020). Probabilistic earthquake and flood loss assessment in the Middle East. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 49, 101662, doi:10.1016/j.ijdr.2020.101662.
7. Debele, S.E.; Leo, L.S.; Kumar, P.; Sahani, J.; Ommer, J.; Bucchignani, E.; Vranić, S.; Kalas, M.; Amirzada, Z.; Pavlova, I.; et al., (2023). Nature-based solutions can help reduce the impact of natural hazards: A global analysis of NBS case studies. *Science of The Total Environment*, 902, doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.165824.
8. European Commission Directorate-General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (ECHO), (2021). Overview of natural and man-made disaster risks the European Union may face; ISBN 9789276293040.
9. Badina, S.; Babkin, R.; Bereznyatsky, A.; Bobrovskiy, R., (2022). Spatial aspects of urban population vulnerability to natural and man-made hazards. *City and Environment Interactions*. 15, 100082, doi:10.1016/j.cacint.2022.100082.
10. European Commission Critical Infrastructure Protection, [Online], Available https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/scientific-activities-z/critical-infrastructure-protection_en (30 July 2023).
11. Langemeyer, J.; Baró, F., (2021). Nature-Based Solutions Nature-based solutions as nodes of green-blue infrastructure networks: A cross-scale, co-creation approach. *Nature-Based Solutions*. 1, 100006, doi:10.1016/j.nbsj.2021.100006.
12. Everard, M.; Ahmed, S.; Gagnon, A.S.; Kumar, P.; Thomas, T.; Sinha, S.; Dixon, H.; Sarkar, S., (2020). Can nature-based solutions contribute to water security in Bhopal? *Science of The Total Environment*. 723, 138061, doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138061.
13. Cioffi, G., (2015). The Terror Risk to Current Water Infrastructure System, York University.
14. Wolfe, M.K. and J. Mennis, (2012). Does vegetation encourage or suppress urban crime? Evidence from Philadelphia, PA. *Landscape and Urban Planning*. 108, p. 112–122, doi:10.1016/j.landurbplan.2012.08.006.
15. Venter, Z.S.; Shackleton, C.; Faull, A.; Lancaster, L.; Breetzke, G.; Edelstein, I., (2022). Is green space associated with reduced crime? A national-scale study from the Global South. *Science of The Total Environment*. 825, 154005, doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.154005.
16. Arnold, C. and M.A. Lasch, (2007). Site and Urban Design for Security Guidance Against Potential Terrorist Attacks FEMA 430;
17. Ogletree, S.S.; Larson, L.R.; Powell, R.B.; White, D.L.; Brownlee, M.T.J., (2022). Urban greenspace linked to lower crime risk across 301 major U.S. cities. *Cities*. 131, 103949, doi:10.1016/j.cities.2022.103949.
18. Regos, A., (2022). Nature-based solutions in an era of mega-fires; *Nature*. 607, 7919: 449-449.
19. Felix, M. and M. Elhefnawi, (2020). Landscape design elements as a defensive tool for building security. In *Advances in Science, Technology and Innovation*; Springer International Publishing: p. 227–238 ISBN 9783030173081.
20. Home Office; Center for the Protection of National Infrastructure; National Counter-Terrorism Security Office, (2012). Protecting Crowded Places: Design and Technical Issues; ISBN 978-1-84987-393-2.
21. RIBA, (2010). RIBA guidance counter-terrorism; London, England;

22. Koccaz, Z.; Sutcu, F.; Torunbalci, N., (2008). Architectural and Structural Design for Blast Resistant Buildings. In Proceedings of the The 14th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering: p. 8.
23. Landscape Architecture Aotearoa Designing to deter attacks - The Sandy Hook case study, [Online], Available <https://www.landscapearchitecture.nz/landscape-architecture-aotearoa/2018/2/27/designing-to-deter-attacks-the-sandy-hook-case-study>.
24. Koskela, H. and R. Pain, (2000). Revisiting fear and place: Women's fear of attack and the built environment. *Geoforum*, 3: 269–280, doi:10.1016/S0016-7185(99)00033-0.
25. Sonti, N.F.; Campbell, L.K.; Svendsen, E.S.; Johnson, M.L.; Novem Auyeung, D.S., (2020). Fear and fascination: Use and perceptions of New York City's forests, wetlands, and landscaped park areas. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*. 49, 126601, doi:10.1016/j.ufug.2020.126601.
26. Hosseinalizadeh, S., (2020). Safer Green Cities - A Study about Vegetation Impacts on Perception of Safety in Green Spaces Case Study, Politecnico di Milano.
27. Lis, A. and P. Iwankowski, (2021). Why is dense vegetation in city parks unpopular? The mediative role of sense of privacy and safety. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*. 59, doi:10.1016/j.ufug.2021.126988.
28. Kumar, P.; Debele, S.E.; Sahani, J.; Rawat, N.; Marti-cardona, B.; Maria, S.; Basu, B.; Sarkar, A.; Bowyer, P.; Charizopoulos, N.; et al., (2021). Earth-Science Reviews An overview of monitoring methods for assessing the performance of nature-based solutions against natural hazards. *Earth-Science Reviews*. 217, doi:10.1016/j.earscirev.2021.103603.
29. Chrysoulakis, N.; Somarakis, G.; Stagakis, S.; Mitraka, Z.; Wong, M., (2021). Monitoring and Evaluating Nature-Based Solutions Implementation in Urban Areas by Means of Earth Observation. *Remote Sensing*. 13, doi:10.3390/rs13081503.
30. BBC, Hacker tries to poison water supply of Florida city [Online], Available <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-us-canada-55989843>.
31. Kovacs, E. Irrigation Systems in Israel Disrupted by Hacker Attacks on ICS [Online], Available <https://www.securityweek.com/irrigation-systems-in-israel-disrupted-by-hacker-attacks-on-ics/>.